

Measurement of Financial Performance of Rupali Bank Limited

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Abstract:

This study's objective is to evaluate Rupali Bank Limited's financial performance. The information is gathered for the years 2016 through 2020 from annual reports of banks. In order to determine the effects of bank size, capital ratio, and total loans on total assets on the dependent variable ROA (Return on Assets), which is regarded as one of the key financial performance indicators, this study employs regression and correlation analysis. The outcome demonstrates that these factors have a significant impact on ROA. Based on regression analysis, the result shows that bank, capital ratio, and total loan on total asset have negative impact on ROA. The findings of this study can assist banks, government, investors, policymakers, and shareholders for making effective decisions and improving the overall performance of financial institution in the future.

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Introduction:

Due to financial market integration, liberalization, and technological advancements in banking services, the global banking sector has seen notable changes in recent decades. These have produced both development prospects and difficulties for banks in sustaining profitability in the current context of escalating competition. A strong and resilient banking industry contributes to the stability of the whole financial system and helps a nation withstand negative shocks. A Thanasoglou et al. (2008), who have studied the impact of bank-specific, industry-related, and macroeconomic determinates on bank performance, have examined the effect of these factors on bank performance. Research on the financial performance of banks typically focuses on the analysis of determinants of banks concerning bank profitability. More recently, Mia et al. (2016) used panel data from 50 south Asian microfinance organizations to demonstrate how financial, economic, and institutional reforms had improved yearly average production by 2.1 percent. Additionally, Cox et al. (2014)) attribute US bank failures between 2007 and 2010 to "poor investment choices and significant exposure to systemic risk channels." There are, however, very few studies that examine how financial reform initiatives affect profitability, particularly for emerging nations like Bangladesh. Since 1980, Bangladesh's banking industry has experienced a number of institutional, regulatory, and legal adjustments. Although some reform measures took place sporadically as early as 1983, Bangladesh's reform plans were mostly conducted between 1900 and 1995. Although these changes have been in place for more than 20 years, no study has been done too far to determine if they have increased or decreased the profitability of the banking industry. Accordingly, it is appropriate, according to Gupta et al. (2006), to assess the financial performance of the Bangladeshi banking industry in terms of profitability indicators before, during, and after financial liberalization. In view of the growing modern issues, particularly those brought on by the most recent global financial crisis, such evaluation can also help policy makers grasp the limitations of the reform measures adopted and develop accommodating policies. Abubakar and others in Bangladesh, the banking industry accounts for around 74% of all financial intermediation in 2014. Prior to reform, the command economy system was characterized by ineffective resource allocation. Government ownership and undue meddling, according to Kouser et al. (2012), steered financing at subsidized rates to a few sectors, including state-owned firms. High interest rates on private lending were the outcome of monopoly power created by restrictions. Due to a lack of prudential controls and legal protection for debt collection, the banking industry has a problem with non-performing loans. According to Quresh et al. (2010) financial reform legislation, the banking environment has undergone significant transformation; yet, the industry continues to struggle with maintaining the required levels of capital adequacy and provisioning for non-performing loans. The primary goal of this study is to examine RBL's financial performance and identify key ratios that constrict it. The capital ratio, total debt to total asset ratio, net working capital ratio, and return on asset ratio are the favorable ratios of banks' performance in this research. The recommendation section gives a general description of the proposals. In conclusion, the Bank must transition from the traditional banking system to a creative one, which entails structural and technical advancement, less harassment of Clint who provides prompt services, minimal leverage, and increased managerial effectiveness. As this is a nationalized bank, the bank should focus on welfare of the country and economic advancement with various social services. An effective utilization of human resources can be a better solution and training facility to unskilled employees.

Literature review:

According to Tarawneh (2020), having large total capital, deposits, loans, or assets does not always imply that a bank will function profitably. The success of banks is positively correlated with appropriate functional effectiveness and appropriate asset management. He

demonstrated how the operational effectiveness and asset management, in addition to bank size, had a large and beneficial influence on the financial performance of the banks beyond the scope of this empirical investigation. According to Ahmad (2019), ROA is used to assess the performance of seven banks. He clarified that research has shown a link between ROA and asset management ratio as well as between bank size and operational effectiveness. One of the most important endogenous elements that affects bank ownership. The results of several research are mostly in agreement that the performance of banks is greatly impacted by the ownership schemes used. Particularly, across banks with different ownership structures, state-owned banks have the weakest operating management efficiency. According to Alchian (2018), state-owned businesses fall short in addressing corporate governance issues compared to private businesses. According to La Porta et al. (2017)'s investigation into the relationship between per capita income and productivity and the percentage of state ownership in the banking industry, the heavier the state ownership in the sector, the more serious the activity of the financial market is and the slower the expansion. Additionally, Grigorian et al. (2010) believed that although foreign banks' input-output efficiency is significantly higher at the beginning of their entry than that of domestic banks', this advantage will gradually disappear once the domestic banks start to adapt to the market and the privatization type. Numerous studies have drawn attention to the statistical relationship between the occurrence of bank performance and the privatization of bank shares. According to Fires et al. (2005), private banks run and are managed more effectively in their home nations than state-owned banks. The commercial performance of these private banks will start to decline as state ownership of their shares rises. According to Williams et al. (2005) and Boubkri, et al. (2005), when bank shares are privatized, bank performance will likely increase. However, other research show that the privatization of ownership isn't flawless at the same time. Other (2005) concur that the strategy of privatization is often used to solve issues brought on by organizational transformation; nevertheless, it will take some time before investment returns can be shown. According to a research by Bpmim et al. (2005) and Clarke et al. (2005), the government is enforcing more and more prohibitions in developing nations. Using the research mentioned above, we may draw the following conclusion about how key issues are resolved through privatization: In order to encourage the elimination of the drawbacks with the lowest performance, the bank can first suitably diminish the state-owned components of the shares. The privatization can greatly raise banks' income, which is the second benefit. However, none of the studies mentioned above take profit-oriented performance into account; they only ever look at operating efficiency or productivity. Many businesses, notably banks, depend on the earnings to survive. In order to prevent a crisis from occurring, most governments would require banks inside the operation to close if they make a loss, as was the case in Norway. A sizable number of studies have assessed the profitability of banks. To our opinion, the majority of them consider the bank's profit efficiency. Fu Juo et al. (2016) examined both the profitability and the profitability change. These studies highlight the determinants of profit success in addition to analyzing it. According to Juoet et al. (2015), profit productivity is developed and broken down into four elements: shifts in technical efficiency, allocation efficiency, technology, and pricing effect. Additionally, Grifell et al. (1999) said that a suitable framework was required to reduce the negative connection between profit and productivity. Particularly, their task is to separate the profit-influencing factors of pricing impact, quantity effect, technical effect, technical efficiency effect, product mix, source mix, and scale effect. Therefore, the Grifell-Tatje et al. (1999) decomposition of profit change model is in an exceptionally high position to discover the causes of their profits and enhance future performance, resulting in future profit increases. Additionally, it need to provide a clearer explanation of where the profit changes come from so that regular managers may devise a plan of action to keep the sector viable. Analysis of factors influencing bank profitability is frequently the subject of research on

financial performance of banks. Studies on bank profitability to data, such as Garcia-studies et al. (2009)'s investigation, have looked at the impact of industry-specific, macroeconomic, and bank-specific variables on bank performance. More recently, Mia et al. (2016) used a panel from 50 South Asian microfinance institutions to show that enhanced institutional, financial, and economic changes led to an increase in yearly average production of 2.1 percent. Additionally, Cox et al. (2014) blame poor investment choices and significant exposure to systemic risk channels for the US bank failures that occurred between 2007 and 2010. However, there are several studies that look at how monetary policies affect profitability, particularly for a developing nation like Bangladesh. Since 1980, Bangladesh's banking industry has seen a number of structural, institutional, and legal adjustments. Bangladesh implements reform measures mostly between 1990 and 1995, while some reform attempts started as early as 1983. Although these changes have been in place for close to twenty years, no study has been done to date to determine if their implementation has increased or decreased the banking sector's profitability. Therefore, it is appropriate to assess the profitability of the Bangladeshi banking sector's financial performance before, during, and after financial liberalization. Such an assessment should also help decision-makers deal with the limitations of the reform measures enacted and adopt some accommodating measures in light of the changing nature of today's difficulties, particularly in light of the recent global financial crisis. The primary measures of profitability—net interest margin (NIM), return on asset (ROA), and return on equity—have received the most attention in the literature on bank performance (ROE) (Flamini and co. 2009). Ho and Saunders (1981) propose a theoretical framework (dealership model) for the determinate of NIM in a remarkably influential research. According to the authors, rate risk and the level of off-market competition both influence the interest margin. A decline in NIM is a sign that the banking sector is operating more efficiently. It may also show a reduction in bank taxes or a greater loan default rate, so it won't necessarily show increased efficiency. Numerous empirical studies look at the factors that affect bank performance. The factors may potentially be internal or external, according to Salim et al. (2016). The inner determinants are linked to management choices made specifically for a bank, such as liquidity level, credit exposure, capital ratio, operational effectiveness, and bank size. The external determinants relate to the industry and include ownership or concentration, regulatory reform initiatives, and macroeconomic variables like inflation, GDP growth, and board money growths. The investigation was restricted by the earlier literature to a certain area. To the best of our knowledge, there isn't a research that has been published that examines how Rupali Bank Limited's performance is influenced by some internal issues. This study is different from the prevailing literature in several ways. First, this study examines the impact of bank size, capital ratio, and total loan on total asset on variable quantity return on asset to judge the bank's overall performance. Second, this study conducts the research by collecting data from Rupali Bank Limited annual report. Moreover, the findings of this study will help banks, government's investors, policymakers, and shareholders for creating effective decisions and improving the performance of monetary institution within the future.

Methodology of the study:

We collected secondary data from the financial accounts over the previous five years and utilised it. The pertinent data was taken from the bank's annual reports' income statements and balance sheets. This analysis uses five years' worth of bank data. A sample of five years' worth of bank data was used to analyze Rupali Bank Limited's financial performance. The income statements and balance sheet for this study were created using secondary data that was taken from the bank's annual reports and financial statements for the five-year period between 2016 and 2020, which were made accessible online by Rupali bank Limited. By using Microsoft Excel this study measures the actual picture of the organization's financial health.

Table- 1: Explanation of Variables

Type	Variable	Sign
Dependent	Return on Assets	ROA
Independent	Bank Size (Total Asset)	BS
Independent	Capital Ratio	CR
Independent	Total Loan on Total Asset	L/TA

Model of the study:

This study measures the impact of bank size, capital ratio and total loan on total asset ratio on the return on asset of Rupali bank Limited by using regression model:

$$ROA = \beta_0 + \beta_1 (BS) + \beta_2 (CR) + \beta_3 (L/TA) + \epsilon$$

Where, β_0 = Constant, $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ = Regression coefficient

Analysis, result and discussion:

Capital Ratio:

Table-2: Capital Ratio

Capital ratio				
2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
12.95: 1	6.91: 1	6.40: 1	1.59:1	2.73:1

Figure-1: Capital Ratio

Both a growing and a falling trend may be seen in the capital ratio of Rupali Bank Limited. A 2.73:1 capital ratio in 2020 indicates that the bank has 2.73 Takas in current assets versus 1 Taka in current liabilities. From the analysis of last 05 years, it can be said that the current asset position of the bank is satisfactory.

Total loan to total asset ratio:

Table-3: Total loan to total Asset ratio

Total loan to total Asset ratio				
2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
.05:1	.10:1	.12:1	.24:1	.30:1

Figure-2: Total loan to total Asset ratio

A company has more debt than assets if the loan-to-assets ratio is larger than one. The firm has more assets than debt if the ratio is less than one. The figure shows that the loan-to-asset ratio is less than one. So, the bank has high ratio of total debt to total asset.

Net working Capital:

Table-4: Net working Capital

Net working Capital (in lakh)				
2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
68665.66	70857.50	76308.73	5137.56	13744.82

Figure-3: Net working Capital

From the analysis it is found that the net working capital of Rupali Bank Limited gradually decreases. In year 2020 the net working capital of the bank is 13744.82 million taka. The working capital position of the bank was not satisfactory.

Return on asset ratio:

Table-5: Return on Asset

Return on Asset				
2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
6.99%	6.14%	5.024%	8.51%	10.83%

Figure-4: Return on Asset

It is found that return on asset is fluctuating during the considering period. In year 2020 it is maximum (10.83%) and in year 2018 it is minimum (5.02%). From the analysis it can be said that the overall return on assets of the bank is satisfactory.

Descriptive Statistics:

Table-6: Results of Descriptive Statistics

	ROA	BS	CR	OE	L/TA
Mean	6.11	9.94E+08	6.11	0.16	0.65
Median	6.40	1.08E+09	6.40	0.12	0.42
Maximum	12.95	1.19E+09	12.95	0.33	1.72
Minimum	1.59	7.41E+08	1.59	0.05	0.33
Std. Dev.	4.45	2.08E+08	4.45	0.11	0.59
Observations	5	5	5	5	5

The mean Return on Asset (ROA) value is 6.116000, which is quite high, while the standard deviation is 4.454333. Total assets are used to calculate Bank Size (BS), which has a mean value of 9.94 and a standard deviation of 2.08 that is extremely high. Capital Ratio (CR) has a mean of 6.116000 and a standard deviation of 4.454333. Again, mean value of Operational Efficiency and Total Loan on Total Assets (L/TA) is 0.168000 and 0.656000 while the standard deviation of both Operational Efficiency and Total Loan on Total Assets (L/TA).

Correlation analysis:

Table-7: Results of Correlation Analysis

	ROA	BS	CR	OE	L/TA
ROA	1.00	0.43	0.09	0.99	-0.32
BS	0.43	1.00	0.68	0.44	-0.84
CR	0.09	0.68	1.00	0.08	-0.88
OE	0.99	0.44	0.08	1.00	-0.34
TA	-0.32	-0.84	-0.88	-0.34	1.00

ROA and Bank Size (BS) have a correlation coefficient of 1, which equals 1. The results of the correlations show that the dependent variable (ROA) and independent variable have a perfect positive connection (BS). Additionally, it is evident from the correlation test that the dependent variable (ROA) and independent variable (CR), which have a 0.095011 correlation, are strongly positively correlated. The correlation coefficient between the dependent variable (ROA) and the independent variable (OE) is similarly quite high and is equal to 0.997052. While there is a

strong negative correlation between the independent and dependent variables (L/TA and ROA), their connection is -0.326714.

Regression Analysis:

Table-8: Results of Regression Analysis

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
BS	-4.55E-23	4.47E-23	1.01	0.49
CR	0.11	0.03	3.42	0.18
L/TA	5.15	1.46	3.51	0.17
C	-3.34	0.47	-7.02	0.09
R-squared	0.99			
Adjusted R-squared	0.99			
F-statistic	769.40			
Probe(F-statistic)	0.02			

ROA with independent variables:

Bank Size:

With a value of -4.55, the link between bank size and ROA is unfavorable. According to this finding, a firm's ROA declines by -4.55 percent for every 1 percent rise in bank size. The size of the bank has a negligible impact on ROA.

Capital Ratio:

The findings show that Capital Ratio also has a negative correlation with ROA, with a coefficient of 0.110343. However, the relationship found in this study has a 0% degree of significance and is statistically significant.

Total loan on total asset:

The data show that total loan on total assets has a strong negative correlation with ROA (5.153315). Additionally, it is discovered that the regression coefficient is statistically negligible.

Multi colinearity Analysis:

Table-9: Multi colinearity Analysis

Variable	Coefficient	Un centered	Centered
	Variance	VIF	VIF
C	1182.173	294.7717	NA
BS	4.56E-16	116.2731	3.949641
CR	1.321905	17.56125	5.231910
L/TA	2.149335	29.47792	7.311200

To further reinforce the reliability of the regression results, a test to identify multicollinearity (variance inflation factor) is also carried out. There should only be 10 Variance Inflation Factors (VIF). Since there is no significant multicollinearity in this case and the VIF values of the BS, CR, and L/TA are all less than 10, we may move further. The table's VIF findings for the model's BS and L/TA variables, which vary from 3.95 to 7.31, indicate that there is no multicollinearity among the model's variables. Results below 10 and close to zero show no multi colinearity, just in case of VIF.

Findings:

Higher total asset might not generate higher profits. The negative coefficient of size means profitability will increase with bank size but at a decreasing rate. It implies that bank is a smaller amount stable. One major finding is that the negative relationship of capital ratio with ROA. Negative and insignificant relationship between capital ratio and ROA suggest that the bank is less profitable. Total loan an asset shows a negative and insignificant relationship with profitability indicator ROA. Overall it's concluded that bank size, capital ratio, and total loan and total asset are the main internal determinates of profitability of Rupali Bank Limited.

Recommendations:

The bank should think about the utilization of its assets within the coming years with the goal that each one asset turn over are going to be increased. Return on asset is that the pointer how bank utilize its assets to form returns. The bank must specialize in increment of ROA. The bank should consider debt to asset with the goal it'll increment. That each one assets turnover is going to be increased. The banks settlement issue is one among the principle reasons of diminishing money gathering. The banks settlement framework is lacking contrasted and different banks. During this way, the bank should build cash trade framework. Director intervention in loan decisions should be minimized because doing so increases risk and contributes to debt growth. Managers at the entry-level should be encouraged to pursue unpaid debts from defaulting customers. Rupali Bank's infrastructure is insufficient to operate the banking sector. Some cops don't appear to have access to the right facilities. This might thus be given special consideration. For the employees to carry out the banking job correctly, there should be the appropriate incentives. Because employee communication and motivation are crucial components of an effective utilization of human resources. Overtime pay is frequently given in accordance with additional working hours. The website's layout needs to be improved. As a result, the website design has to be modified and might include additional bank information. The customer's attention cannot be drawn by the current design.

Conclusion:

Effective and innovative industry is required for sustainable economic process so, it's indispensable to spot the determinants/indicators that have an influence on the performance of banks. This study investigates the impact of independent variables on banks return on asset (ROA) which is taken as a measurement of Rupali bank limited overall performance. Rupali bank limited is taken as study area. Bank size, capital ratio and total asset are taken as independent variables which return on asset is taken as variable quantity. The findings also reveal that banks have extensive assets can gain safety and competitive advantage and thus have better financial performance, supported indirect correlation with bank size, it are often concluded that the bank incorporates a reduced amount of deposit and hence can't be ready to perform banking operations efficiently. On the idea of multivariate analysis, it's found that the interior indicators including bank size, capital ratio and total loan on asset are negatively correlated with ROA.

Policy implication:

The study findings would be great help to the policy-measures, practitioners, research, academicians and to other stakeholder. It gives internal and external stakeholders the ability to make well-informed investment decisions. Additionally, financial performance analysis gives lending institutions a frank assessment of a company's financial standing, which is helpful in making loan decisions. It helps the users like owners, lenders, employees, suppliers, and government agencies to measures the bans profitability and performance. Additionally, the analyses of the bank's financial performance are often a useful source of knowledge for future researchers.

Future work:

Future research is often extended by exploring another model to check the influence of internal variables on banks' overall performance. Researchers also can consider other internal factors similarly as some external factors. They'll also increase the sample size or take into consideration by combining some commercial banks to conduct the research.

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